

Metal Complexes of *p*-Dimethylaminoanil of Phenylglyoxal

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Isolation and properties of a number of complexes of *p*-dimethylaminoanil of phenylglyoxal (PDAAP) have been described. Based on magnetic moments, electronic spectra, infra-red spectral studies and molar conductance, the structures of these compounds have been discussed.

CO-ORDINATION ability of different Schiff bases derived from glyoxals and their analytical applications have been studied extensively.¹⁻⁶ However, Schiff bases derived from glyoxals and aromatic amines have not been fully investigated till now. Recently Schiff bases derived from phenylglyoxal hydrate (and β -naphthylglyoxal hydrate) and primary aromatic amines have been reported by Malik and Saxena^{1,2}. *p*-dimethylaminoanil of phenylglyoxal (I) was prepared by Kronke and Gross³. In the present studies, chelate compounds of PDAAP with Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Co(II) and Ni(II) have been studied.

Experimental

The ligand PDAAP was prepared by condensing phenylglyoxal (0.01M) ethanolic solution and *p*-dimethylaminoaniline (0.05M)-ethereal solution at room temperature, m. p. 70° (Found: C, 75.00; H, 6.24; N, 10.99; C₁₃H₁₄N₂O requires: C, 75.41; H, 6.34; N, 11.11 percent). Structure of the ligand (I), indicates its bidentate nature.

All metal chlorides used were of A. R. quality.

Bausch and Lomb spectronic "20" spectrophotometer was used for the measurements of absorbances of acetonic solutions of the complexes. Electronic spectra of these complexes were also recorded in nujol mull on a Cary-14 recording spectrophotometer. Conductance experiments were made with a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. Magnetic measurements were done in a Gouy balance which was calibrated with mercury-tetra-thiocyanato cobaltate (II). The IR spectra in the solid state were taken in KBr disc with the help of Perkin Elmer 137 IR spectrophotometer.

Isolation of the complexes

(a) Dichloro-bis-(*p*-dimethylaminophenylglyoxalanilato) Ti(IV) chloride :

* For correspondence.

Equimolar solutions of TiCl₄ and *p*-dimethylaminoanil of phenylglyoxal in acetone were mixed in stoichiometric ratio 1:2. The reaction mixture was placed in vacuum dessicator over calcium chloride when violet coloured crystals of dichloro-bis-(*p*-dimethylaminophenylglyoxalanilato) Ti(IV) chloride complex separated. These crystals were washed several times with acetonitrile and were finally dried in vacuum. The complex decomposed at 100°.

(b) Dichloro-bis-(*p*-dimethylaminophenylglyoxalanilato) Zr(IV) chloride :

Equimolar acetonic solutions of ZrCl₄ and ligand were mixed in 1:2 ratio. Violet coloured crystals were obtained on evaporating the mixture in vacuum. Decomposition point 205°.

(c) Dichloro-bis-(*p*-dimethylaminophenylglyoxalanilato) Th(IV) chloride :

Procedure (a) was adopted to obtain pink coloured crystals, decomposition point 160°.

(d) Dichloro-bis-(*p*-dimethylaminophenylglyoxalanilato) Hf(IV) chloride :

Procedure (b) was adopted and pink coloured crystals of the complex were isolated; decomposition point 190°.

(e) Dichloro or Dibromo-bis-(*p*-dimethylaminophenylglyoxalanilato) Co(II) :

Green coloured crystals were obtained by refluxing the stoichiometric mixture of Co(II) chloride/bromide and the ligand in the ratio 1:2, in ethanol solution on waterbath for 1.5 hr. The complexes decomposed above 300° :

(f) Dichloro or Dibromo bis-(*p*-dimethylaminophenylglyoxalanilato) Ni(II) :

On adopting the procedure (e) (with NiCl₂/NiBr₂) pink coloured crystals of the complex were isolated⁷; decomposition point above 360°.

In table I are listed colour and elemental analyses data of the complexes.

TABLE 1—COLOUR AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex Compound	Colour	% Elemental Analysis				
		Calcd. (Found) C	Calcd. (Found) H	Calcd. (Found) N	Calcd. (Found) Halogen	Calcd. (Found) Metal
[Ti(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Violet	55.32 (55.20)	4.61 (4.51)	8.06 (7.90)	20.46 (20.31)	6.91 (6.80)
[Zr(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Violet	52.08 (52.20)	4.34 (4.25)	7.59 (7.48)	19.26 (19.15)	12.37 (12.22)
[Th(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Pink	43.73 (43.62)	3.64 (3.51)	6.37 (6.25)	16.17 (16.00)	26.42 (26.30)
[Hf(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Pink	46.58 (46.40)	3.88 (3.72)	6.79 (6.76)	17.18 (17.00)	21.66 (21.52)
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	Green	60.57 (60.25)	5.04 (5.14)	8.83 (8.64)	11.04 (10.98)	9.29 (9.38)
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	Green	53.13 (53.25)	4.42 (4.28)	7.74 (7.61)	22.14 (22.00)	8.14 (8.22)
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	Pink	60.59 (60.33)	5.04 (5.10)	8.83 (8.70)	11.04 (10.85)	9.29 (9.36)
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	Pink	53.15 (53.21)	4.42 (4.30)	7.74 (7.58)	22.14 (22.25)	8.14 (8.05)

Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF solution and magnetic moments were measured in powder form.

TABLE 2

Complex Compound	λ_m ohm ⁻¹ cm ² (in DMF)	μ_{eff} (B.M.) at 30°.
[Ti(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	150	0.19
[Zr(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	165	0.09
[Th(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	178	0.25
[Hf(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	154	0.23
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	30	4.50
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	38	4.90
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	45	3.00
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	50	3.60

Results and Discussions

Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Th(IV), Hf(IV), Co(II) and Ni(II) form 1:2 complexes with PDAAP. Composition of the complexes was confirmed by elemental analysis, magnetic moment and molar conductance. Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV) and Th(IV) having electronic configuration 3d⁰, 3d¹⁰, 4d¹⁰, and 5d¹⁰ should exhibit magnetic moment (0.0-0.50 B. M.) in octahedral complexes⁶. The complexes exhibit molar conductance in the range (140-280 ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹ cm²) of biunivalent electrolytes⁸. Co(II) and Ni(II) having electronic configuration 3d⁷ and 3d⁸ should exhibit magnetic moments (4.7-5.3 B. M.) and (3.0-3.3) respectively in octahedral complexes. Substantial solvolysis occurs in DMF. Table 3 reports the electronic spectral data of complexes. (nujol-mull, cm⁻¹ and in acetonic solutions).

In the electronic spectra of [Co(C₁₀H₁₆N₂O)₂Cl₂] and [Co(C₁₀H₁₆N₂O)₂Br₂] three distinct bands appear at 9,000-8,203 cm⁻¹ (ν_1), 20,000-16,800 cm⁻¹ (ν_2) and

TABLE 3

Complex Compound	λ_{max} .cm ⁻¹	Splitting energy Δ cm ⁻¹	Racah Parameter B cm ⁻¹	Nephelauxetic Ratio β
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ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES (NUJOLMULL CM⁻¹)

[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	25,000 20,000 9,000	10,530	1097	0.98
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	21,012 17,310 8,203	9,610	1001	0.99
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	28,571 17,857 10,870	10,870	921	0.85
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	28,830 17,945 10,670	10,670	984	0.91

ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF IN ACETONIC SOLUTION

[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	24,500 19,300 8,850	10,368	1080	0.96
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	21,000 16,800 8,540	9,984	1040	0.93
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂]	28,000 17,500 10,150	10,150	1003	0.93
[Ni(C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	28,170 17,200 10,230	10,230	979	0.90

Value of B for Ni(II) and Co(II) was taken as 1080 and 1120 respectively¹¹

25,000—21,000 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) respectively which are assigned to transitions ⁴T_{1g} (F)→⁴A_{2g} (F), ⁴T_{1g} (F)→⁴T_{1g} (P) with spin orbit split of ⁴T_{1g} (P) state and a charge transfer band in the ultraviolet region. Thus octahedral symmetry¹⁰ for Co(II) complexes is suggested. Inter-

electronic repulsion parameter B and splitting energy parameter $10 D_q$ were calculated by Figgis equations¹¹

$$\frac{{}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)}{B} = 8.2$$

$$\frac{D_q}{B} = 0.96$$

The spectra of $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O})_2\text{Br}_2]$ exhibit three absorption bands with peaks at $10,870\text{-}10,150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_1); $17,945\text{-}17,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2) and $28,830\text{-}28,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) respectively. These bands may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. This suggests octahedral structure for Ni(II) complexes in weak ligand field¹⁰. Octahedral symmetry is further confirmed by the ratio ν_2/ν_1 which lies between 1.6-1.8 for this symmetry¹²⁻¹⁴.

Interelectronic repulsion parameter was calculated using diagonal sum rule.

$$15B = \nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1$$

and β was evaluated for Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes by the relation

$$\beta = \frac{B \text{ in complex}}{B \text{ in free ion}}$$

Infrared spectral studies: In the i. r. spectra of these complexes the stretching frequencies of ketonic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ (1700 cm^{-1}) and azomethine $\text{CH}=\text{N}$ (1600 cm^{-1}) groups are lowered, showing thereby chelation through these groups. This view is further supported by the appearance of bands at $490\text{-}520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $450\text{-}480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the formation of M-N and M-O bonds. In all these complexes metal-halogen bonds are also formed, it is revealed by the appearance of bands around $350\text{-}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

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